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Pseudoaneurysm formation after placement of a FRED flow diverter stent in a patient with iatrogenic ICA injury during transsphenoidal surgery: A case report

Pseudoaneurysm formation after placement of a FRED flow diverter stent in a patient with iatrogenic ICA injury during transsphenoidal surgery: A case report. - Abstract - Europe PMC Sign in | Create an account <https://orcid.org> Europe PMC Menu About Tools Developers Help Contact us Helpdesk Feedback Twitter Blog Tech blog Developer Forum Europe PMC plus Search life-sciences literature (43,274,544 articles, preprints and more) Search Advanced search Feedback This website requires cookies, and the limited processing of your personal data in order to function. By using the site you are agreeing to this as outlined in our privacy notice and cookie policy. Abstract Full text Pseudoaneurysm formation after placement of a FRED flow diverter stent in a patient with iatrogenic ICA injury during transsphenoidal surgery: A case report. Hasanpour M 1 , Golchin N 2 , Mirsardoo H 1 , Alagha A 3 , Elyassirad D 4 , ...

Keywords: FRED flow diverter stent, Iatrogenic ICA injury, Pseudoaneurysm

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